

Copper(II) Azide and Tetrafluoroborate Complexes with Substituted Imidazoles

CH. KRUSHNA C. MOHAPATRA† and KAILASH C. DASH*

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Vani Vihar, Bhubaneswar-751 004

Manuscript received 26 April 1978, revised 20 July 1978, accepted 6 October 1978.

Complexes of copper(II) azide and tetrafluoroborates were prepared with several substituted imidazoles. The complexes were either planar and four-coordinated as in $\text{CuL}_2(\text{N}_3)_2$ (L=1-Vinyl, 2-Isopropyl, 2-Ethyl imidazole) or tetragonal and six-coordinated as in $\text{CuL}_4(\text{N}_3)_2$ (L=1-Methyl, 2-Methyl imidazole) and $[\text{CuL}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2]$ (L=1-Vinyl, 2-Methyl, 2-Isopropyl imidazole). The compounds do not have any Cu-Cu interaction, as is clear from the experimental magnetic moments lying in the 1.7–1.9 B.M. range. The i.r. spectra provided evidence for unsymmetrical coordination of the azide ion, N_3^- , as well as suggested the coordination behaviour of the BF_4^- ion.

AS a part of our investigations on the complexing ability of imidazole and its derivatives,^{1,2} we report here the complexes of several 1- or 2-substituted or 1, 2-disubstituted imidazoles with copper(II) azides and tetrafluoroborates. The bonding properties of the azide, N_3^- and tetrafluoroborate, BF_4^- can be studied on the basis of the vibrational spectroscopy. The BF_4^- ion may not coordinate to the metal and remain "ionic", may coordinate to the metal in a monodentate or bidentate manner or may remain in a situation

which is somewhat intermediate between these two extreme types of bonding. The last mode of coordination is known as "semi-coordination", evidence for which is presented here for some of the tetrafluoroborate complexes of copper(II).

Results and Discussion

The complexes isolated are shown in Table I, along with their colour, decomposition temperature,

TABLE I—COPPER(II) COMPLEXES WITH IMIDAZOLES AND THEIR CHARACTERISING DATA

Compound	Colour	Decomposition Temp. (°C)	Found (Calcd.)%		μ_{eff}^* (B.M.)	ΔM^* ($\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$)
			Cu	N		
$\text{Cu}(1\text{-MeIm})_2(\text{N}_3)_2$	Green	187	12.9 (13.3)	40.8 (41.1)	1.71	54.3 ^a
$\text{Cu}(1\text{-ViIm})_2(\text{N}_3)_2$	Green	120	18.4 (18.8)	40.9 (41.6)	1.72	28.6 ^a
$\text{Cu}(2\text{-MeIm})_2(\text{N}_3)_2$	Green	155	13.2 (13.3)	40.7 (41.1)	1.70	69.9 ^b
$\text{Cu}(2\text{-EtIm})_2(\text{N}_3)_2$	Green	165	18.3 (18.6)	40.8 (41.2)	1.72	16.5 ^a
$\text{Cu}(2\text{-IPrIm})_2(\text{N}_3)_2$	Green	148	17.1 (17.2)	37.7 (38.0)	1.74	14.6 ^a
$\text{Cu}(1\text{-MeIm})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Pink	190	7.9 (8.7)	22.6 (23.0)	1.75	260.3 ^a
$\text{Cu}(1\text{-ViIm})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Blue	105	9.9 (10.3)	17.9 (18.2)	1.76	185.2 ^a
$\text{Cu}(1\text{-Vi } 2\text{-MeIm})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Blue	168	6.9 (7.1)	18.7 (18.9)	1.83	183.8 ^c
$\text{Cu}(2\text{-MeIm})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Deep blue	204	11.1 (11.2)	19.6 (19.8)	1.90	189.8 ^c
$\text{Cu}(2\text{-EtIm})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Pink	204	10.1 (10.2)	17.6 (18.0)	1.74	190.9 ^c
$\text{Cu}(2\text{-IPrIm})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	205	6.9 (7.0)	18.4 (18.7)	1.83	178.6 ^c

Abbreviations: Me=Methyl; Et=Ethyl; Vi=Vinyl; Ipr=Isopropyl and Im=Imidazole

* Measurements at room temperature.

a) Acetone, b) Methanol, c) Nitromethane

† B. J. B. College, Bhubaneswar-751016

* Author for correspondence.

analytical and conductivity data as well as room temperature magnetic moment data. These complexes belong either to a four-coordinate, square planar geometry or to a six-coordinate, tetragonal stereochemistry. All these compounds have either a green or blue colour, except only in two cases, where the colour is pink, probably due to a strong charge-transfer band in the U. V. region tailing off into the blue end of the ultra-violet spectrum.

The conductivity values of the complexes in Me_2CO , MeOH and MeNO_2 solutions^{3,4} indicate that all the azide complexes are non-electrolytes and the tetrafluoroborate complexes, in general, behave as 1 : 2 electrolytes. The azide complexes have molar conductivity values ranging from 14.6 to 69.9 mho $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$ in either Me_2CO or MeOH medium. These values are substantially lower than the values expected for a 1 : 1 electrolyte in these solvents, but are somewhat higher than that expected for a non-electrolytic complex. This higher value of conductivity for some of the complexes might have arisen due to solvolysis to a certain extent. The observed magnetic moments of these complexes is in the 1.7-1.9 B.M. range, which is in agreement with the general range for the copper(II) complexes⁵. The regular tetrahedral complexes of copper(II) have magnetic moments of ca. 2.2 B.M.⁶ and show no d-d absorption bands in the region 10,000-20,000 cm^{-1} . Since none of the compounds exhibit these characteristics, it is assumed that this stereochemistry is not observed in the present series of complexes.

The octahedral Cu^{II} complexes have a $2e_g$ ground state and are, as a rule, due to Jahn-Teller distortion, distorted tetragonally with four shorter coplanar bonds and two longer axial bonds⁹. Meek and Ehrhardt⁹ have observed that the squareplanar complexes have a complex broad band at relatively higher frequencies (15,000-20,000 cm^{-1}), while the octahedral complexes have a diffuse band in the 13,000-18,000 cm^{-1} region and a band at around 21,000-23,000 cm^{-1} . In agreement with this, the four-coordinate copper(II) complexes reported here exhibit a band at around 15,000 cm^{-1} suggesting a planar structure and the six-coordinate tetragonal complexes exhibit a band at around 22,000 cm^{-1} .

Further information regarding coordination around the Cu^{II} ion is obtained on the basis of vibrational spectroscopy, which provides information regarding the mode of bonding of the azide and tetrafluoroborate anions. Ionic azide group, N_3^- , which is symmetrical and centrosymmetric ($D_{\infty h}$) exhibits i.r. active bands at 2041 and 645 cm^{-1} respectively for asymmetric stretching and bending vibrations,^{10,11}. On coordination, the symmetry of the azide ion is destroyed and an asymmetric azide group ($C_{\infty v}$) shows very strong stretching band just above 2000 cm^{-1} , a relatively weak stretching band above 1300 cm^{-1} and another band due to bending just above 600 cm^{-1} .¹² All the

azido complexes reported here showed strong absorption bands in the 2020-2060 cm^{-1} region (usually two sharp bands) due to the asymmetric stretching vibration and a band of moderate intensity at 630-635 cm^{-1} region due to the bending motion¹³. The symmetric stretch was observed in most cases as a band of weak or moderate intensity at around 1320-1325 cm^{-1} . This evidence is indicative of terminal coordination^{13,14} and thus, the bis-complexes, $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{N}_3)_2]$ ($L=1\text{-ViIm}$, 2-IPrIm , 2-EtIm), are square-planar and the tetrakis complexes, $[\text{CuL}_4(\text{N}_3)_2]$ ($L=1\text{-MeIm}$), are six-coordinated distorted octahedral in structure.

In the i.r. spectra of all the hexakis complexes of the type $[\text{CuL}_6](\text{BF}_4)_2$ ($L=1\text{-MeIm}$, 1Vi-2MeIm , 2-EtIm , 2-IPrIm), no sign of splitting of the ν_3 (asymmetric stretching) frequencies could be observed and always a very strong but broad band centred at around 1060 cm^{-1} was observed, indicating the ionic character of the BF_4^- anion (T_d symmetry)¹⁵. However in case of the tetrakis complexes, $\text{CuL}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$ ($L=1\text{-ViIm}$, 2-MeIm), the i.r. spectra of the anion seems to be somewhat intermediate in type between those of the free and of the covalently bonded tetrafluoroborate group. The ν_3 mode showed signs of weak splitting and bands were obtained at 1040, 1060 and 1092 cm^{-1} , demonstrating evidence in favour of "semi-coordination", where the BF_4^- anion is perhaps involved in very weak bonding in long tetragonal positions, thus distorting its symmetry only to a smaller extent. Similar effect was observed earlier for $\text{Cu en}_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$ ¹⁶. Thus, six-coordinated tetragonal complexes are obtained in both the cases of $[\text{CuL}_4](\text{BF}_4)_2$ and $\text{CuL}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$ and in the latter case this coordination number is achieved through the weak coordination of the BF_4^- anion in long axial positions.

Experimental

All physical measurements and analyses were carried out as described in an earlier paper².

Syntheses of Complexes

All the chloro complexes were prepared by published methods¹ and wherever necessary, were used as the starting materials.

$\text{CuL}_2(\text{N}_3)_2$ ($L=1\text{-ViIm}$, 2-EtIm , 2-IPrIm) and $\text{CuL}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$ ($L=1\text{-ViIm}$, 2-EtIm) complexes were prepared by reacting the respective chloro complexes in methanol with an excess of NaN_3 or NaBF_4 in minimum volume of water. The resulting solutions were stirred and concentrated. The highly soluble NaCl was retained in solution and removed. On concentration, the desired complex separated out, which was collected on a frit, washed with ethanol, then ether and finally dried in *vacuo*.

$\text{CuL}_4(\text{N}_3)_2$ ($L=1\text{-MeIm}$, 2-MeIm), $\text{Cu}(2\text{-MeIm})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$, and $\text{CuL}_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$ ($L=1\text{-MeIm}$, 1-Vi-2-MeIm ,

2-IPrIm) were prepared by reacting an ethanolic or methanolic solution of cupric chloride and the required ligand, followed by the addition of an excess of NaN_3 or NaBF_4 in minimum amount of water. The mixture was stirred, refluxed for ca. 30-60 min., concentrated to almost half its volume and then kept overnight. In some cases, it was necessary to add isopropyl alcohol to crystallise the solid compounds.

References

1. Ch. K. C. MOHAPATRA and K. C. DASH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1253.
2. K. C. DASH and Ch. K. C. MOHAPATRA, *Transition Metal Chem.*, 1977, **2**, 155.
3. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
4. N. S. GILL and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3997.
5. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd. Edn., Interscience, New York (1972), 916.
6. B. N. FIGGIS, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 1568.
7. A.B.P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam (1968), 359.
8. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw Hill, New York, 1962, 268.
9. D. W. MEEK and S. A. EHRHARDT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 584.
10. P. GRAY and T. C. WADDINGTON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 901.
11. H. A. PEPAZIAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **34**, 1614.
12. I. AGRELL, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1970, **24**, 1247.
13. G. HERZBERG, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Polyatomic Molecules", Van Nostrand, New York (1945).
14. J. S. THAYER and R. WEST, *Adv. Organometallic Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 169.
15. B. J. HATHAWAY and D. E. WEBSTER, "Proc. Chem. Soc." 1963, 14.
16. D. S. BROWN, J. D. LEE, B. G. A. MELSON, B. J. HATHAWAY, I. M. PROCTER and A. A. G. TOMLINSON, *Chem. Comm.*, 1967, 369.